

A Study on Developments in Education Sector with the aid of Advanced Information and Communication Technology

Krishna Prasad K.

College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangaluru-575001,
Karnataka, India

E-mail: krishnaprasadkcci@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

ABSTRACT

A good Education is a well-defined process of acquiring skills, facilitating learning, obtaining special values, beliefs or habits, which results in overall individual growth of a person. Nowadays a student can learn new concepts without actually visiting the traditional classroom and sitting anywhere, anytime, or ubiquitously with the aid of advanced developments in Information and communication technology. Education technology helps to improve the performance by using and managing appropriate technological tools or process, or resources with the aid of several domains like learning theory, computer based training, online learning, and m-learning. Normally educational technology can be classified as Hardware approach, Software approach, Systems approach. Hardware approach uses some special physical equipment like microphone, which is essential to make voice audible to a big crowd or audience and helps the teacher to make his teaching very effective. In these context audio-visual aids such as slides, charts, models, graph, and some of the electronic gadgets like radio, television, filmstrips, projectors, video, and high-speed computers are successfully used in order deliver educational contents to the audience or students and to make the teaching very effective. The second type of educational technology is mainly based on behavioral sciences and this type of technology adopt process based techniques with an ultimate intention to produce high-quality teaching-learning content or material, special teaching or learning strategies or assessment technologies. The third type of educational technology is based on computer engineering and usually referred to like the system. In this type of educational technology is developed and designed based well defined sophisticated systematic methods with an aim to evaluate the overall process of education with specific objectives. This approach takes education as a system with a set of inputs which are focused on a certain process and designed to process certain outputs which should meet some predetermined objectives. This paper covers different types of educational technology under three major types as hardware, software, and system. This paper also covers all these types of advantages, benefits, constraints, disadvantages.

Keywords: *Education Technology, ICT, Teaching aids, Hardware Approach, Software Approach, System Approach.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Technology in education is service concepts like technology in transport, technology in services with the aid of special hardware, software, or system which improves the overall performance or effectiveness of education. A good Education is a well-defined process of acquiring skills, facilitating learning, obtaining special values, beliefs or habits, which results in overall individual growth of a person [1]. Nowadays a student can learn new concepts without actually visiting the traditional classroom and sitting anywhere, anytime, or ubiquitously with the aid of advanced developments in Information and communication technology [2]. Normally educational technology can be classified as Hardware approach, Software approach, Systems approach. Hardware approach uses some special physical equipment like microphone, which is essential to make voice audible to a big crowd or audience and helps the teacher to make his teaching very effective. In these context audio-visual aids such as slides, charts, models, graph, and some of the electronic gadgets like radio, television, filmstrips, projectors, video, and high-speed computers are successfully used in order deliver educational contents to the audience or students and to make the teaching very effective [3]. The second type of educational technology is mainly based on behavioral sciences and this type of technology adopt process based techniques with an ultimate intention to produce high-quality teaching-learning content or material, special teaching or learning strategies or assessment technologies. The third type of educational technology is based on computer engineering and usually referred to like the system.

This paper runs under six sections. The first section describes about introductory part of educational technology under three approaches as hardware, software and system. The second section describes about types of educational technology, and tries to find difference between technology in education and technology of education. The section three narrates about why student need technology inside classroom or how technology helps in students learning. The section four describes bundles of technologies that assists teachers to deliver the content of teaching more effective and efficient manner. The bundle of technology involves Projector, Radio, Television, Slides, Models, Charts, Graphs, Filmstrips, Online video, Virtual reality and many more. The section five analyzes educational technology approaches through Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages. Section six concludes the paper.

2. TYPES OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

The Educational Technology is usually classified into two as;

1. Technology of Education
2. Technology in Education

1. Technology of Education: It is inherent or natural in education itself which is not derived or exported from any external source. It refers to behavioral science and applications of teaching and learning practices used by the teacher to deliver the content in more understandable way to students [4]. It focuses on solving the educational problems and the

different techniques used in teaching learning problems with an ultimate goal to make the students understandable in more effective and easily. Not only the teaching but also the techniques of planning, financing, and administration are also included in technology of education. Techniques of curriculum planning, teaching, learning, and evaluating also come under technology of education. The technology of education generally includes or covers following techniques;

Planning and Analysis or Examination of Instructional problems

- Selection of instrument or process or special methods for evaluation
- The various strategies adopted to obtain desired result from the teaching learning process.
- The behaviour of the teacher
- Programmed learning techniques
- System analysis

2. Technology in Education: Technology in education involves the use of special implements, tools, machines, or computer systems as like we use these for the cultivation and development of agriculture, industry, or day to day life with an intension to reduce human interaction and to fill the gap between scientific technology and education [5]. Technology in education includes electronic media projector, film, radio, teaching machine, computer, TV and Internet.

Technology in education is the application of engineering principles and various types of technologies which work together to attain some goals in education. The origin of technology in education lies in physical science or engineering principles, whereas technology of education lies in behavioural science [6]. The technology in education makes the teacher or instructor sometimes lethargic, but innovation in technology makes the education more affective and interesting [7-8]. The Table 1 shows differences between Technology of education and Technology in education.

Table 1: Differences between Technology of Education and Technology in Education

Areas	Technology of Education	Technology in Education
1. Basis	Based on the physiological behaviour of the teacher.	Based on the principles of physical science and engineering technology and smart machines

2. Approach	The approach is usually logical in nature and also can be identified as software approach	The approach is physical in nature which we can see and feel and also can be identified as hardware approach
3. Origin	Its origin is based on application of behaviour science based problems	Its origin is based on physical science and engineering to education.
4. Examples	Textbook, Workbook, newspapers, evaluation software	TV, Projector, Computer, OHP, Filmstrips, Video, Models.
5. Relation	It's related to learning aids and which helps to improve learning efficiency.	It's related to teaching aids and which helps to improve teaching efficiency.
6. Requirement	In order to handle this approach does not require skilled persons.	In order to handle this approach require skilled persons unlike software approach
7. Flexible	This approach not more flexible in nature	This approach is more flexible in nature
8. Type	Here constructive educational technology is utilized	Here relative educational technology is utilized.
9. Application or Contribution to educational system	This approach is very helpful in understanding the need of the learners or students and educating them based on their ability	It is applicable in mass education programmes and can be reached to large audience.
10. Cost	This approach is less expensive	This approach is expensive.

3. WHY STUDENTS NEED TECHNOLOGY IN CLASSROOM?

Following are the various reasons in support of use of technology in classroom.

- Nowadays smart mobile phone comes with various applications or apps which helps and assists the students in teaching and learning process. The challenge is to monitor the usage of mobile phones because lot of non-educational contents also delivered through mobile devices.
- Integrating technology with classroom makes students all over the world single group with students of various learning styles and behaviours.
- Technology in education helps the students in team management, team building by interacting with their classmates and instructors.

-
- Using technology in classroom makes or builds a platform for teachers and all other types of faculty members to enhance and develop student's eco-friendly, paperless digital content development skills. At the same time usage of mobile devices monitored and controlled safely, correctly and responsible way.
 - Integrating technology with education makes the students more engaged because all the students' community have been engaged in using mobile phones most of the time.
 - Integrating or combining classroom with virtual reality is a live example to demonstrate how the technology influences and enhances the teaching learning experience of both students and teachers and creates new opportunities.
 - Through Wi-Fi enabled classroom and mobile technology students can able to access most updated information
 - Through the adoption technology in education traditional passive learning model is vanished and teacher becomes only encourager, guide or a coach.
 - Technology helps the students to become more creative, interactive, responsible, and connected.

4. BUNDLE OF TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

Technology helps the instructor or teacher to deliver teaching or education content easily and at the same time helps the students to understand the concept effectively and interestingly. Through the involvement of technology practical understanding of the concepts can be improved to more extent. The various technologies used in Education are Projector, Radio, Television, Slides, Models, Charts, Graphs, Filmstrips, Online video, Virtual reality and many more. A Projector is devices which works on optical rays or light that project or focuses an ideal image or moving image onto a white space or board or screen. In radio usually some online programs are scheduled which helps the students to update their information and to acquire new knowledge. Like radio in Television also some educational programs are telecasted which helps the students to get more knowledge and information. A slide is a one page where information are presented to the audience and group of such slides are referred as slide deck or power point presentation. Charts are diagrammatic representation or pictorial representation of data in which numerical values are represented by symbols like bar, line or pie.

M-learning is new learning model of e-learning, with the help of smart mobile phones and wireless networks. The initial Mobile learning system was based on Short Message Service, which also provided voice services along with SMS. M-learning is a new paradigm in which interaction between students and teacher improved without any barriers to classroom. Brown et al. conducted a case study on mobile learning environment using web2.0 and mobile devices, in order to explore how mobile technologies and social softwares can be used for collaborative learning, sharing, understanding and building virtual communities by considering different user requirements for the university students. Mobile learners can use SMS to transmit some limited amount of text between learners or to internet server and usually most of the students owns mobile phone, but only few students owns PDA.

Bailey et al. demonstrated interactive and active learning techniques helps learners to acquire new knowledge, develop reasoning and critical thinking, responds to a problems differently and independently than others, where as in passive learning is on the teaching principle of transferring knowledge from teachers to students in verbal forms [9]. Podcast- a downloaded series of audio or video files via computer is an effective revision tool compare to students their own note or text books and students having provision of flexibility to read notes anywhere, anytime [10-11]. Ubiquitous learning system includes five types of situation parameters as Personal situation sensors, Environmental sensors, Feedback sensors, Personal database, Environmental database and some models of conducting ubiquitous learning includes real world learning with online guidance, evaluation by identifying real world objects, real world observation with the help of online data searching and cooperative problem solving [12-13]. Using fourth generation mobile communication technology mobile learners can access learning materials like interactive courses, virtual online labs, interactive online testing and lab exercise training platform by utilizing all-IP communication networks and which uses variety of computer embedded devices in order to access multimedia information [14-15].

5. ANALYSIS OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

The Educational Technology can be classified as Hardware approach, Software approach, and System approach as discussed earlier in this paper. This Educational Technology can be analyzed using Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and disadvantages [16-24].

Advantages

- Promotes, develops, or cultivates independent or self learning environment in students.
- Students not only understands the current concepts but also prepared for the future.
- The dependency of the textbook can be reduced to major extent.
- Faculty or Teacher teaching efforts can be reduced.
- Allows or helps the teachers to create exiting or attractive teaching content or curriculum.
- Teachers are encouraged or self motivated to use new teaching methods or aids.
- Hardware approaches like microphone, makes teacher voice audible to a big crowd or audience and helps him/her to make teaching very effective
- Software approach adopts process based techniques with an ultimate intention to produce high-quality teaching-learning content or material, special teaching or learning strategies or assessment technologies.
- System approach enriches teaching and learning environment more effective through computer engineering process.

- Services are not restricted to four walls of classroom, can be accessed ubiquitously.
- One Material can be used for all states or province of a country, with each states added information
- Highly updated informative competitive examination material can be prepared.

Benefits

- Improves or enhances student's engagement and concentration within or inside a classroom.
- Through visual and audio presentations students can remember the concepts for a longer duration.
- Through mobile and online learning educational technology also encourages or supports individual learning capacity of students.
- Having great ability to acquire new customers because of passionate and dynamic services.
- No time and place restrictions, learners can get services anywhere, anytime.
- Global standard can be maintained in content or material.
- Student Friendly environment
- Student having control over the delivery of content especially in online learning.
- Educational technology makes then whole classroom collaborative using new and modern technology aids.

Constraints

- Educator or teachers should have skills to use modern teaching technology or gadgets especially in hardware approach.
- The contents and curriculum prepared by the teachers should have high quality and standards.
- Students centered approaches rather than Teacher centered approach.
- If technology fails entire class collapses
- Lack of student and teacher one to one interaction or eye contact in case of online mode of education.
- In online learning mode Monitoring students or learners becomes tedious task.
- Implementation cost is high in online learning.

Disadvantages

- Negative or misconceptions like technology are meant for entertainment rather than education.
- Instructional challenges are sometimes not positively accepted by the trainers or teachers or instructors.
- Can reduce the one-to-one relationship in big classroom when teachers use more technology aids for teaching and learning.
- Because of online mode of education and all contents are accessible through mobile or computer classroom room teaching exhibits lack of interest in students.

6. CONCLUSION

Integrating technology in education in a proper way makes the teaching learning process attractive and more affective. Education technology helps to improve the performance by using and managing appropriate technological tools or process, or resources with the aid of several domains like learning theory, computer based training, online learning, and m-learning. In this paper, the first section describes about introductory part of educational technology under three approaches as hardware, software and system. The second section describes about types of educational technology, and tries to find difference between technology in education and technology of education. The section three narrates about why student need technology inside classroom or how technology helps in students learning. The section four describes bundles of technologies that assists teachers to deliver the content of teaching more effective and efficient manner. The bundle of technology involves Projector, Radio, Television, Slides, Models, Charts, Graphs, Filmstrips, Online video, Virtual reality and many more. The section five analyzes educational technology approaches through Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages. Section six concluded the paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bates, A. W., & Poole, G. (2003). *Effective Teaching with Technology in Higher Education: Foundations for Success*. Jossey-Bass, An Imprint of Wiley. 10475 Crosspoint Blvd, Indianapolis, IN 46256.
- [2] Bonk, C. J. (2009). *The world is open: How web technology is revolutionizing education* (pp. 3371-3380). Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE).
- [3] Bates, A. W. (2000). *Managing Technological Change: Strategies for College and University Leaders*. The Jossey-Bass Higher and Adult Education Series. Jossey-Bass Publishers, 350 Sansome St., San Francisco, CA 94104.

- [4] Yusuf, M. O. (2005). Information and communication technology and education: Analysing the Nigerian national policy for information technology. *International education journal*, 6(3), 316-321.
- [5] Papert, S. (1987). Information technology and education: Computer criticism vs. technocentric thinking. *Educational researcher*, 16(1), 22-30.
- [6] Fabry, D. L., & Higgs, J. R. (1997). Barriers to the effective use of technology in education: Current status. *Journal of educational computing research*, 17(4), 385-395.
- [7] Bates, A. T., & Sangra, A. (2011). *Managing technology in higher education: Strategies for transforming teaching and learning*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [8] Kay, R. H. (2006). Evaluating strategies used to incorporate technology into preservice education: A review of the literature. *Journal of research on technology in education*, 38(4), 383-408.
- [9] Bailey, D (2004). Active learning. In R. Hoffman (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of educational technology*, <http://coe.sdsu.edu/eet/Articles/activelearning/index.htm>. Accessed 20 March 2015.
- [10] K. Krishna Prasad and P.S. Aithal (2015). Mobile System for Customized and Ubiquitous Learning by 4G/5G. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 5(7), 63-71.
- [11] Krishna Prasad K. & Dr. Aithal, P. S. (2016). Changing Perspectives of Mobile Information Communication Technologies towards Customized and Secured Services Through 5G & 6G. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 1(2), 210-224.
- [12] Krishna Prasad, K. and Aithal, P. S. (2017). A Study on Online Education Model Using Location Based Adaptive Mobile Learning. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 1(1), 36-44. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.820457>.
- [13] Krishna Prasad, K. and Aithal, P. S. (2017). A Customized and Flexible Ideal Mobile Banking System Using 5G Technology. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMITS)*, 1(1), 25-37. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.820457>.
- [14] Krishna Prasad K. & Dr. Aithal, P.S. (2016). The Growth of 4G Technologies in India- Challenges and Opportunities. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 6(1), 543 - 551, (January 2016) ISSN: 2249-0558, I.F. 5. 299. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161130>.
- [15] Krishna Prasad, K. & Aithal, P. S. (2016). An Online Comparative Study on 4G Technologies Service Providers in India. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJATET)*. 1(1), 96-101. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.240269>.

- [16] Aithal P. S, Shailashree V. T., Suresh Kumar P. M., (2015). A New ABCD Technique to Analyze Business Models & Concepts. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 5 (4), 409 – 423.
- [17] Aithal, P. S. (2016). Study on ABCD Analysis Technique for Business Models, Business strategies, Operating Concepts & Business Systems, *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 4(1), 98-115. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161137>.
- [18] Aithal, P. S. and Pai T, Vaikunta (2016). Concept of Ideal Software and Its Realization Scenarios. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 826-837.
- [19] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T. & Suresh Kumar, P. M., (2016d). Analysis of ABC Model of Annual Research Productivity using ABCD Framework. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(1), 846-858. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.62022>.
- [20] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). A New ABCD Technique to Analyze Business Models & Concepts.
- [21] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Suresh Kumar P. M., (2016a). ABCD analysis of Stage Model in Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 6(1), 11-24. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.154233>.
- [22] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016b). Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System in India. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR)*, 5(4), 159-170. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161111>.
- [23] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016c). The Study of New National Institutional Ranking System using ABCD Framework, *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(1), 389–402. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161077>.
- [24] Aithal, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2016). ABCD analysis of Dye doped Polymers for Photonic Applications, *IRA-International Journal of Applied Sciences*, 4 (3), 358-378. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21013/jas.v4.n3.p1>.